

**ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATIONAL
LESSONS FOR BIOLOGICAL STUDENTS**

Norova Nafisa Farkhodovna

**Researcher, Department of Pedagogy, Shahrizabz State Pedagogical
Institute, nafisaxonfarxodovna1@gmail com
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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the organization of independent educational lessons for biology students. Independent learning plays a key role in developing students' scientific thinking, research skills, and ability to make independent decisions. The study highlights methods such as laboratory exercises, interactive approaches, project- and problem-based learning, digital technologies, and competency-based approaches to enhance the effectiveness of independent lessons. The results show that well-organized independent learning improves students' practical and laboratory skills, fosters creative and critical thinking, and prepares highly qualified, competitive specialists for the future.

Introduction. Today, the education system is aimed not only at imparting theoretical knowledge to students, but also at forming them as professionals with practical skills, able to think independently and professionally prepared. This requirement is especially important in biology, since biology is a science aimed at studying the life processes of living organisms and their interdependence, in which the student must be able not only to acquire theoretical knowledge, but also to develop his own independent observation, analysis and research activities. For biology students, the process of independent learning is an important tool for forming their scientific thinking, developing research skills, and strengthening their ability to independently solve complex scientific problems. At the same time, the student himself participates in the process as an active subject, combining theoretical knowledge with laboratory exercises and practical research. Independent learning classes create the opportunity for students to effectively manage their time, study complex topics in depth, conduct experiments and experiments, analyze results, and draw conclusions. The modern educational process is enriched with digital technologies and interactive pedagogical methods, which develop students' creative and critical thinking skills. For example, through virtual laboratory exercises, interactive simulations, and project work, students have the opportunity to apply their knowledge in practice. At the same time, the student's independent learning process increases his personal initiative, sense of responsibility, time management skills, and ability to conduct scientific research. From this point of view, the organization of independent learning classes for biology students is not only an increase in the efficiency of the educational process, but also an integral part of training highly qualified, competitive specialists who will conduct scientific research in the future. The process of independent learning teaches

students to solve real scientific problems through scientific research, experiments and laboratory experiments. Therefore, the organization of independent learning classes in biology on a proper methodological basis, enriched with interactive and digital technologies is a task of strategic importance for improving the quality of the educational process, preparing students for scientific and professional activities, and forming them as competitive specialists in the future labor market.

The organization of independent learning lessons for students in biology is important not only for strengthening their theoretical knowledge, but also for developing scientific thinking, research skills, and creative thinking. An analysis of scientific literature shows that the effective organization of independent learning requires a combination of pedagogical, methodological, and technological approaches [1]. The authors recommend methods for developing students' scientific research and independent thinking skills by combining the process of independent learning with laboratory exercises and interactive methods in biology lessons [2]. Modern pedagogical technologies and competency-based approaches explore the possibilities of effectively organizing the process of independent learning. The journal covers the issues of stimulating active and independent learning of students, increasing learning efficiency through the use of problem-based and interactive methods [3]. It provides recommendations on the psychological aspects of the student's independent learning process, time management, responsibility, and initiative skills [4]. The importance of competency-based approaches and methodological tools in the formation of independent learning is scientifically demonstrated [5]. It highlights methods for involving students in independent learning, problem-based learning tasks, and increasing the effectiveness of project-based learning [6]. Interactive methods and assessment systems are recommended for teaching students to work independently, developing their critical thinking and scientific research skills [7]. An analysis of this literature shows that interactive methods, laboratory exercises, project and problem-based learning, digital technologies, and competency-based approaches are important factors in organizing independent learning lessons for biology students. Also, psychological preparation, time management, and motivation are among the main factors that make a student's independent learning effective. At the same time, the literature shows that independent learning plays a decisive role not only in consolidating knowledge, but also in preparing the student for scientific thinking and research activities.

Main results. The conducted analyses and pedagogical observations showed that the effective organization of independent learning lessons for biology students has a significant impact on their educational process and professional preparation. Through independent lessons, students have the opportunity not only to consolidate their theoretical knowledge, but also to develop scientific thinking and practical skills through laboratory exercises and practical assignments. The process of independent learning forms in students the skills of conducting scientific research, identifying problems and solving them independently. At the same time, the student's ability to make independent decisions and personal initiative increases, he learns to effectively manage his time and acquires the skills to systematically complete assignments. The use of modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, project work and digital tools encourages students to actively learn, develops creative and critical thinking skills, and also increases the efficiency of the educational process. Through

independent study classes, students will have the opportunity to set their professional goals, conduct scientific research, and strengthen the necessary preparation to become competitive specialists in the future. Therefore, organizing independent study classes for biology students based on systematic and interactive approaches is of great importance in developing their scientific thinking, strengthening practical skills, increasing creative and critical thinking skills, and preparing highly qualified and competitive specialists in the future.

The conducted analysis and literature review show that organizing independent study classes for biology students is an important factor not only in strengthening theoretical knowledge, but also in developing students' scientific thinking, research skills, creative and critical thinking skills. The independent study process allows students to effectively manage their time, study complex topics in depth, and gain practical experience in laboratory exercises. At the same time, the student's independent decision-making, problem-solving, and teamwork skills develop, and personal initiative and a sense of responsibility increase.

Conclusion. Modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, project work and the use of digital tools increase the activity of students in the learning process, encourage them to think independently and creatively. In independent learning lessons, through problem-based tasks, laboratory experiments and project work, students learn to conduct their own scientific research, analyze the results obtained and draw conclusions. At the same time, digital portfolios and electronic diaries allow you to monitor, evaluate the student's activities and clearly demonstrate the acquired knowledge.

For the effective organization of independent learning in biology, a combination of pedagogical, methodological and technological approaches is necessary. Interactive methods, laboratory exercises, project and problem-based learning, digital technologies and competency-based approaches are of primary importance in student activities. Also, the student's psychological preparation, time management skills and motivation are important factors that make independent learning effective. As a result, the effective organization of independent learning classes for biology students develops their scientific thinking, strengthens practical and laboratory skills, increases creative and critical thinking, and in the future serves to train competitive and highly professionally trained specialists. Therefore, universities should modernize the pedagogical process and organize independent learning classes in an interactive, project-based and digital technology-enriched form. This not only increases the quality of the educational process, but also prepares students to conduct scientific research, develop professional skills, and be competitive in the labor market. In general, the organization of independent learning classes for biology students is an integral and most important part of the modern education system. This process is crucial for combining the student's theoretical knowledge with practice, forming professional and scientific competencies, developing creative and critical thinking, and improving the quality of education.

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